

Station: Working Conditions Usage

Select your scenario!

from **A** (working conditions good (few blocks))
to **D** (working conditions bad (many blocks))

1x ≙ Low salaries / financial dependancy

3x ≙ Exhausting working conditions, including mental stress

5x ≙ Several exhaustive work steps

Guiding questions:

The guiding questions will help you to gradually understand the differences between the scenarios and maintain an overview.

No
blocks

A

B

C

D

I visit social media sites.

No

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Yes

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I post content on social media.

No

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Yes

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I follow influencers on social media.

No

Yes

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I listen to music using streaming services (Spotify, Apple Music, YouTube, ...).

No

Yes

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I use generative AI or digital assistants (Siri, ...).

No

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Yes